

USING MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS AN INDEPENDENT STUDY

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Abstract

this article deals with innovative methods of teaching English and learning this language independently as well as several notions about independent study are given.

Key words: independent study, self-education, creative level, empirical, cognitive motives, critical.

A few of the authors' methodologists and psychologists describe motivation as a person's distinctive cognitive orientation to objects and phenomena of reality. In terms of the methodical construction of educational and cognitive motivation, this problem may be seen as the purpose of education and rising. When an English instructor draws attention to a topic with the aid of amusing aspects provided at various phases of the class, he is using motivation as a method of teaching and rearing. In this instance, the student has a new motivation for the educational activity: he wants to hear the teacher's explanation. The instructor goes on to set the purpose of teaching English to create this new motive, and it is now tough for the pupil to conduct more sophisticated mental work, but it is intriguing. This work is becoming more closely related with self-education. Motivation already acts as a function of training and upbringing in this case. This, in our opinion, enables the English language instruction system to include all three aspects of motivation as a goal, method, and outcome. Theoretical theory differentiates between episodic and persistent motivations. The first appear episodically over the course of action and fade away with its conclusion. The latter are distinguished by their stability, independence from specific circumstances, and encouragement to work in one's subject of interest under all circumstances. It should be mentioned that the desire to do anything to improve their understanding of foreign language culture is just the first, albeit crucial, step in the development of long-term motivation and the need for self-education.

The appropriate utilization of independent work unquestionably has enormous reserves for enhancing educational and cognitive drive. Knowing the benefits of autonomous labor, we must determine its application to the topic "English" as a communicative process. It is typical in the approach to define three stages of

autonomous work: replicating (copying); semi-creative; and creative. When learning English, the replicating level of autonomous work is critical since it underpins the other levels and is “responsible” for the building of the pronunciation-lexical-grammatical basis, as well as the generation of samples in the student's memory. In reality, absorption of the new begins at this point. Students are given options such as reading after a speaker, copying from a textbook, and “passing through” new content during self-reproduction. However, when arranging this level of autonomous work, the instructor should bear in mind that it is not essential to retain pupils in such work for an extended period of time since it is tedious and repetitive; At the same time, pupils must be able to accurately and at a regular pace duplicate the acquired language and speech content that they will need to address more complicated issues. The semi-creative level of autonomous labor follows the replicating level in terms of execution complexity. The learned information, skills, and talents are transferred to different but comparable settings, namely reading words, phrases, sentences, and texts without the speaker's sample, not only copying from a textbook, but transforming the content in writing and, lastly, forming remarks in similar situations. This degree of independent labor necessitates greater mental engagement from the performer and is connected with processes such as substitution, expansion, and transformation.

The creative level of independent work is associated with the development of skills and abilities to search when solving more complex communicative tasks, both in oral speech and when reading, such as acting in accordance with the proposed circumstances and the role assumed, preparing a message on a specific topic, listening to the message and expressing your attitude to its content, reading the story, and answering problematic questions related to the content and semantics. These levels coexist in the practice of autonomous work in English, and each can be represented by a distinct collection of sublevels. Educating students who have a strong interest in foreign language culture and the need for self-education is a complex process that includes the study of a student's personality, motivations for his behavior, and teaching, all of which are required for the development of individual inclinations and interests in all students. Many difficulties linked to the solution of these problems are thoroughly investigated and addressed in current methodological theory.

According to researchers, the development of specific methodological material for students should include: - differentiated tasks for independent work of varying degrees of difficulty; - options for short-term and long-term programs of self-

education and self-education for students; - methodological guidelines and recommendations for the study of some of the most difficult issues, topics, and problems of the curriculum; - programs of informative conversations, evenings, and dissections for students. Each instructor solves the challenge of forming pupils' educational and cognitive motives in connection to foreign language culture by taking into consideration individual conditions and chances. However, the broad methodological principles of the problem-solving approach allow us to differentiate three major levels of problem-solving, which may or may not constitute stages of the progressively complicated process of building cognitive motivation. The first is empirical in nature. It is based on an experienced understanding of the need for the development of cognitive motivations in children, as well as the idiosyncrasies of their development at various levels of the lesson, during extracurricular activities, and so on.

The second level is more creative, with aspects of research. The tasks that the instructor proposes for himself get more sophisticated at this level of activity, and as a result, the requirements placed by the teacher on pupils and the amount of material for independent work become more intricate. Research is the greatest degree of issue resolution. It blends scientific principles and a creative mindset with a research method to studying students' interests, preferences, and talents. At this stage, the most ideal conditions for the creation and development of students' educational and cognitive motives are produced, taking into consideration their state of health and degree of prior training. Creative pedagogical thinking is founded on a thorough independent study of scientific pedagogy, psychology, and a variety of related disciplines of knowledge, best practices in teaching and educating students, pedagogical introspection, and the keeping of diaries of observations of their daily work. Famous methodologists such as E.I. Passov, G.V. Rogova, L.P. Malishevskaya, and others have made major contributions to the theory and practice of scientific organization and independent work, allowing us to delineate the key stages of cognitive interest growth and education. The following are phases in carrying out the job itself in the lesson:

1. Preparatory, in which the instructor informs students about the aim of their work, discloses the prospects for more successful execution, and allows everyone to contact him for guidance or to utilize supplementary reading if necessary. This stage assumes that the teacher has prepared various literature in advance, with special attention paid to the relationship of three factors in the formation of teaching motives: - assisting the student in mastering the skills and abilities of

independent creative work; - constant encouragement to this mastery; - creating conditions for the manifestation and development of acquired skills and abilities in the process of working on various tasks as part of a training and complicated task.

2. The process of the pupil working independently in the classroom. It is necessary not only to occupy the student with mental work and encourage him to meet certain requirements, but also to ensure the necessary development of the student's interest in mental activity, a gradual transition from work of a reproducing nature (according to samples) to a more complex one, requiring the use of skills and skills of using reference books, dictionaries, and, finally, to independent creativity, requiring the manifestation of imagination and skilfulness.

3. Summary-generalizing, allowing autonomous work in the classroom to be included in a more or less sophisticated form of homework.

To have a systematic influence on the rearing and development of general and particular educational interest in foreign language culture, a system of classroom and homework assignments geared for short-term and long-term performance must be developed. Independent work can be done in a variety of ways, including alone, in pairs, in small groups, and as a class. Each of these forms is intended to foster and improve students' organizational, informational, cognitive, and communicative abilities, mastery of which will assure students' growth in language acquisition in tandem with the development of their technique. Modern methodologists place a premium on this part of autonomous work, regarding the development of students' techniques as a necessity for continued education. According to G.V. Rogova, developing pupils' autonomous activity in English learning is difficult unless the following requirements are met. To begin, it is vital to understand the aim of the activity being performed, as well as each individual exercise. The learner should understand what he will perform, in what order, what the end outcome will be, and how this job will enhance his experience. The student must accept the task in order for the correct effect to be achieved. The use of the principle of consciousness in the structuring of the student's autonomous work is nothing more than awareness of the aim of the activity (exercise). Second, familiarity with the task execution method is essential. In this scenario, there is also a dependence on the principle of consciousness, i.e. knowledge not only of the significance of the work, but also of its execution process. Third, the ability to employ relevant learning instruments to perform the task, such as sound

recording, educational didactic material for pair work, and so on, is required. As a result, students must master the technical training tools offered in the language laboratory in order to complete assignments on the language workshop. Fourth, it is vital to be able to recognize the supports in the material of tasks that assist overcoming problems in the course of autonomous work; in this case, it is also necessary to understand how to utilize ready-made (objective) examples as well as build your own (subjective). Fifth, it is critical to establish proper didactic settings for effective autonomous task performance, which means first determining the appropriate location for them: in the classroom, at home, or in the language lab. When the teacher introduces students to rational methods of completing the task, it is preferable to do this work in the classroom; if technical means of training are required, which students do not have at home, it is preferable to do this work in the language lab; otherwise, it is preferable to do this work at home. This should involve the selection of organizational forms for carrying out a certain sort of autonomous activity. [2] No matter how talented a student is, it is impossible to grasp English even in a tightly limited volume if he studies it once or twice a week. Only daily, methodical work supervised by the instructor in terms of its content, shape, methods, and execution techniques is now an urgent requirement and yields the required outcomes.

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